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PRIMARY BILIARY CHOLANGITIS: MODERN ASPECTS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract:

Primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) is a chronic progressive autoimmune liver disease characterized by the gradual destruction of intrahepatic bile ducts. The consequence of this process is cholestasis, fibrosis, and ultimately, liver cirrhosis. Despite the rarity of the pathology, it remains an important issue in modern hepatology, as early diagnosis and proper treatment can significantly improve patients' quality of life and slow the progression of complications.

Keywords: primary biliary cholangitis, cholestasis, symptoms, treatment.

Relevance: Primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) is one of the most common chronic liver diseases of autoimmune origin, which, without proper treatment, leads to progressive fibrosis, cirrhosis and liver failure. The incidence of PBC is increasing worldwide, especially among middle-aged women, making the problem relevant to modern hepatology [1].

Despite significant progress in understanding the pathogenesis and development of new therapies, some patients do not respond to standard ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) therapy, which necessitates the search for alternative approaches. In addition, timely diagnosis, a personalised approach to therapy, and prevention of complications, such as osteoporosis, portal hypertension, and liver failure, are important aspects.

The relevance of the study is due to the need to update diagnostic algorithms, introduce the latest methods for assessing the course of the disease and improve treatment strategies that can improve the prognosis and quality of life of patients with PBC [2].

Materials and methods: The study analysed current scientific articles and clinical guidelines on primary biliary cholangitis (PBC). The sources used include international studies, guidelines of the European Association for the Study of the Liver (EASL) and clinical observational data.

The purpose of the work is to evaluate current approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) based on the analysis of scientific sources, including the effectiveness of therapy and the possibility of improving the prognosis for patients.

Results and discussion: The main reason for the development of PBC is a malfunction of the immune system, which leads to an attack of autoantibodies on the intrahepatic bile ducts. In most patients, antimitochondrial antibodies (AMA) are detected, which play a key role in damaging liver cell structures.

Mechanisms of the disease include: genetic predisposition - studies indicate a link between PBC and specific genes of the major histocompatibility complex (HLA-DRB1); autoimmune processes - the presence of concomitant autoimmune diseases, such as Sjögren's syndrome, autoimmune thyroiditis, scleroderma; environmental triggers - possible exposure to viral infections, toxins and bacterial super-antigens that can trigger an autoimmune reaction. As a result of the inflammatory process, small bile ducts are destroyed, toxic bile acids accumulate in the liver tissue, and fibrosis gradually develops, which can lead to cirrhosis [7].

The clinical picture of PBC develops slowly, and its symptoms may remain unnoticed for many years. In

50-60% of cases, the disease is detected incidentally during routine laboratory tests [5,6].

The main clinical manifestations of PBC:

- Itchy skin is one of the first symptoms that occurs due to the accumulation of bile acids in the blood.
- Chronic fatigue - observed in most patients, reduces the quality of life.
- Jaundice - appears in the later stages when significant cholestasis develops.
- Hepatomegaly (enlarged liver) and splenomegaly (enlarged spleen) - can be detected during the examination.
- Xanthomas and xanthelasma - fatty deposits on the skin associated with lipid metabolism disorders.
- Pain in the right hypochondrium - usually moderate, may be recurrent.
- In the later stages, complications develop: liver cirrhosis, portal hypertension, osteoporosis, malabsorption syndrome (deficiency of fat-soluble vitamins - A, D, E, K) [5,6,7].

The diagnosis of primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) involves a thorough analysis of clinical manifestations, laboratory tests and instrumental methods. The disease often develops slowly, with a gradual progression of cholestasis, so in the early stages, symptoms may be mild. Patients often complain of fatigue, itchy skin, dry mouth, which may be accompanied by jaundice of the skin and sclerae. In case of suspected PBC, an important step is to determine biochemical markers, such as increased levels of alkaline phosphatase (ALP), gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (GGT), bilirubin, and cholestatic enzymes. The most characteristic laboratory findings are an increase in ALP and GGT in the absence of a significant increase in transaminases. 90-95% of patients have antimitochondrial antibodies (AMA), which are a marker of the autoimmune nature of the disease. Positive AMA results provide important support for the diagnosis, but are not sufficient to confirm PBC. In cases where an AMA result is absent or not sufficiently informative, other specific markers such as antinuclear antibodies (ANA) and antibodies to bile duct salts can be used. Instrumental diagnostics include liver ultrasound to detect changes characteristic of cholestasis, such as an increase in the size of the liver and bile ducts. Non-invasive assessment methods, such as elastography or ultrasound elastography, are used to determine liver fibrosis, allowing for assessment of liver stiffness and fibrosis stage without the need for biopsy. Liver biopsy remains the gold standard for confirming the diagnosis and assessing the stage of fibrosis, but due to possible complications, it is usually used in complex cases or in cases of doubtful diagnosis. To better assess the severity of the disease, clinical indices such as the MELD (Model for End-Stage Liver Disease) prognostic model are used to assess the risk of disease progression and the need for liver transplantation [6,7,8,9].

The treatment of primary biliary cholangitis (PBC) is aimed at reducing cholestasis, slowing the progression of liver fibrosis, preventing complications and improving the quality of life of patients.

Basic therapy: Ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) is a first-line drug that reduces bile stasis, protects hepatocytes from damage and has an immunomodulatory effect. It is prescribed at a dose of 13-15 mg/kg/day. Long-term use (throughout life) improves biochemical parameters of liver samples and slows down the progression of the disease. At an early stage, PBC can significantly reduce the risk of cirrhosis and liver failure. About 30-40% of patients do not achieve a complete biochemical response to UDCA, which requires additional therapy [3,4].

Adjunctive therapy for patients who do not respond to UDCA: Obeticholic acid (OBA) is an FXR receptor agonist that reduces bile acid production in the liver and improves bile flow. It is prescribed at a dose of 5-10 mg/day. It effectively reduces the level of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and bilirubin. Side effects: skin itching, increased low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels. It is not recommended for patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis [3,4]. Fibrates (fenofibrate, bezafibrate) are PPAR- α receptor activators that reduce inflammation and facilitate bile acid excretion. They are used as an adjunct to UDCA in patients with an insufficient response. They have a positive effect on liver function tests and reduce the severity of pruritus. Side effects: possible negative impact on renal and muscle function [3,4].

Symptomatic therapy: Itchy skin - treated with antihistamines, cholestyramine or rifampicin. Fatigue syndrome - there is no specific therapy yet, physical activity and psychosocial support are recommended. Osteoporosis - control of vitamin D and calcium levels, use of bisphosphonates if necessary [4]. Liver transplantation. The only treatment for end-stage PBC when liver failure or severe refractory pruritus develops. Indications for transplantation: elevated bilirubin levels >6 mg/dl, decompensated cirrhosis, encephalopathy. The 10-year survival rate after transplantation is about 80-85%. Recurrence of PBC after transplantation is possible in 20-30% of cases [4]. The prognosis and quality of life in PBC has improved significantly thanks to modern therapies. With timely treatment, many patients can live for more than 20 years without significant deterioration in liver function. At the same time, late detection of the disease or lack of treatment can lead to rapid progression of cirrhosis and the development of liver failure [9,10].

Conclusions: Primary biliary cholangitis is a serious chronic liver disease that requires early diagnosis and lifelong therapy. Adherence to treatment recommendations, regular liver monitoring and correction of concomitant disorders are important. Further research is aimed at developing new drugs that will improve the prognosis for patients with this disease. Thanks to modern treatment methods, most patients can lead a full life, avoiding serious complications.

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